

Synthesis of some New 2-Thioxoquinazolin-4-ones

M. B. DESHMUKH (HOGALE)*, D. S. DESHMUKH and (MRS.) S. D. SHIRKE

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004

Manuscript received 19 May 1995, revised 16 November 1995, accepted 19 January 1996

Quinazolines exhibit important physiological activities¹. Here we report the synthesis of some new 3-substituted-thiocarbamate derivatives of 2-thioxoquinazolin-4-one.

Scheme 1. Reagents : (ia) ClCH₂COOCH₃/K₂CO₃, acetone, (ib) CH₃-CHCl-COOCH₃/K₂CO₃, acetone, (ii) NH₂NH₂·H₂O/ethanol and (iii) Ph-N=C=S/ethanol.

Results and Discussion

3-Aryl-2-thioxo-4(3*H*)-quinazolinone (1) on reaction with methyl chloroacetate and methyl 2-chloropropionate gave 3,4-dihydro-3-(substituted-phenyl)-4-oxo-2-quinazolinone thioacetic/thiopropionic acid alkyl esters (2a₁-h₁) and (2a₂, 2b₂, 2d₂, 2h₂) respectively, which on separate

reaction with hydrazine hydrate furnished the corresponding 3-aryl-2-thioacetylhydrazidoquinazolin-4-one (3a₁-h₁) and 3-aryl-2-thiopropionylhydrazidoquinazolin-4-one (3a₂, 3b₂, 3d₂, 3h₂). Compounds 3a₁-h₁ and 3a₂, 3b₂, 3d₂, 3h₂ on reaction with phenyl isothiocyanate gave the desired thiocarbamates (4a₁-h₁) and (4a₂, 4b₂, 4d₂, 4h₂) respectively.

Experimental

All m.ps. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-437 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (TFA/DMSO-d₆) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of compounds was checked by tlc (silica gel G). Dithiocarbamate salt was prepared by reacting substituted anilines with carbon disulphide in presence of triethylamine².

3-Aryl-2-thioxo-4(3H)-quinazolin-4-one (1a): A mixture of dithiocarbamate salt of substituted aniline in ethanol (10 g, 0.1 mol) and anthranilic acid (15 g, 0.1 mol) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 5 h. The excess solvent was then removed under reduced pressure. The separated solid was redissolved in ethanolic NaOH, filtered and the filtrate on neutralisation with dilute HCl gave a solid which was crystallised from ethanol, (88.7%), m.p. 240° (Found : C, 67.16; H, 4.48, N, 10.45. C₁₅H₁₂ON₂S requires : C, 67.10; H, 4.5; N, 10.30%); ν_{max} 3 250 (NH), 1 660 (C=O), 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 6.8-8 (8H, m, ArH), 13.0 (1H, sbr, NH). Similarly, other quinazolinones (yields 84-97%) were prepared : 1b, m.p. 262°; c, 286°; d, 248°; e, 288°; f, 220°; g, 253°; h, 256°.

*Methyl [3,4-dihydro-3-(*o*-methylphenyl)-4-oxo-quinazolinyl]thioacetate* (2a₁): To a solution of quinazolinone 1 (0.1 mol) and methyl chloroacetate (0.1 mol) in acetone (50 ml), K₂CO₃ (0.5 g) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for ~18 h on an oil-bath. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and cooled to get a solid which was crystallised from ethanol, (70.13%), m.p. 106° (Found : C, 62.42; H, 4.70; N, 8.2. C₁₈H₁₆O₃N₂S requires : C, 62.2; H, 4.8; N, 8.4%); ν_{max} 1 750 (C=O), 1 700-1 690 (cyclic C=O), 1 620 (C=N) cm⁻¹; δ 2.35 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 3.7 (3H, s, O-CH₃), 4.0 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 7-8.1 (8H, m, ArH). Similarly, other compounds (yields 61-85%) were prepared : 2b₁, m.p. 132°; c₁, 122°; d₁, 100°; e₁, 68°; f₁, 78°; g₁, 140°; h₁, 242°; a₂, 100°; b₂, 242°; d₂, 158°; h₂, 246°.

NOTE

3,4-Dihydro-3-(o-methylphenyl)-4-oxo-2-quinazolinylthioacetic acid hydrazide (3a): A mixture of **2** (0.1 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (80%; 0.1 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 3 h at 70°. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure to get a solid which was crystallised from ethanol, (83.7%), m.p.138° (Found: C, 60.0; H, 4.71, N, 16.47. C₁₇H₁₆O₂N₄S requires : C, 60.2; H, 4.8; N, 16.2%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 250 (NHNH₂), 1 680 (C=O), 1 660 (C=O), 1 600 cm⁻¹; δ 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 3.7 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 4.8 (2H, s, NH₂), 7–7.5 (8H, m, ArH), 10.5 (1H, s, CONH). Other hydrazides (yields 52–94%) were prepared similarly : **3b**₁, m.p.135°; **c**₁, 148°; **d**₁, 195°; **e**₁, 208°; **f**₁, 196°; **g**₁, 170°; **h**₁, 255°; **a**₂, 112°; **b**₂, 203°; **d**₂, 280°; **h**₂, 230°.

The thiocarbamate derivatives (4a₁): A mixture of **3** (0.1 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.1 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h on a steam-bath and the excess of solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and cooled. The resulting solid was crystallised from etha-

nol, (63.7%), m.p.175° (Found : C, 65; H, 4.74; N, 15.8. C₂₄H₂₁O₂N₅S requires : C, 65.2; H, 4.74; N, 14.5); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 300 (NH), 1 680, (C=O), 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 2.35 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 3.7 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 4.8 (br, s, 2×NH), 7–7.65 (13H, m, ArH), 10.5 (1H, s, CONH). Similarly, other thiocarbamates (yields 50–68%) were prepared : **4g**₁, m.p. 58°; **h**₁, 56°; **b**₂, 62°; **d**₂, 55°; **h**₂, 59°.

References

1. H. YAMMAMOTO, Jap. Pat. 6917136/1969 (*Chem Abstr* 1969, 71, 123505); H. YAMMAMOTO, M. NAKAO and E. SCOTIONE, US Pat. 3479348/1970 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1970, 73, 117448); H. ZEUGNER, M. PAILER and PRACKMAYR, Aust. Pat. 228204/1963 (*Chem Abstr.*, 1963, 59, 1251); T. O. YELLIN, US Pat. 3635971/1972 (*Chem Abstr.*, 1972, 76, 99708); I. AHAMED, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1988, 65, 362; A. KUMAR, B. SINGH, A. K. SAXENA and K. SHANKAR, *Indian J Chem, Sect B*, 1988, 27, 443; S. SAXENA, M. BHALLA, M. VERMA, A. K. SAXENA and K. SHANKAR, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1991, 68, 142.
2. R. LAKHAN and M. SRIVASTAV, *Proc Indian Acad Sci (Chem Sci)*, 1993, 105, 11.